
THE MENACE OF ACID MINE DRAINAGE: AN IMPENDING CHALLENGE IN THE MINING OF LAFIA-Obi COAL, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Acid mine drainage (AMD) is one of the most significant environmental challenges facing the mining industry worldwide. It occurs as a result of natural oxidation of sulphide minerals contained in mining wastes at developmental, operating and closed/decommissioned mine sites. This contamination occurs when moving fresh surface water interacts with the rock through fissures, pores and faults, and over time it is changed chemically. These changes often make the water less than ideal for domestic use, and in extreme cases it can be dangerous. AMD may also adversely impact the surface water in streams and groundwater quality and land use due to its typical low pH, high acidity and elevated concentrations of metals and sulphate content. The development of AMD must be put under check because once it develops at a mine; its control can be difficult and expensive. Many a mining environment especially coal mining areas have suffered degradation as a result of acid mine drainage. The proposed Lafia-Obi coal mine which is expected to provide the much needed coking coal for the Adjaokuta Steel Industry cannot be an exception to such environmental menace. The expected coal mining activities has the capacity to affect the quality of domestic water supply to the Nasarawa state capital and its environment with possible unpleasant socio-physiological consequences if not appropriately controlled. The paper provides an early diagnosis of the expected environmental problems associated with mining in addition to identification of appropriate prevention/control and/ or remediation measures and implementation of these methods to the site to reduce the potential risk of AMD generation.

KEYWORDS- Acid mine drainage, lineaments, Hydrological center, Fractures

Methodology

There is paucity of information on the detailed geological investigations on the Obi coal and especially information with regards to the geological work carried out by successive government organizations and consultants firms. To this effect, the data accessed had to be crossed examined by Landsat maps. This is goggle earth Satellite image of the study area downloaded from Google Earth and into ILWIS Software for digitalization of the rivers/ tributaries, roads, contours and fracture zones or lineaments. From the contour map it was converted to point map and a table was created for the longitude, latitude and elevations above sea level. Following which the table was exported to golden Sufur 8 to grid table which was further used to develop a 3D map of the Lafia Obi coal area to provide the required surface water run-off map. The information generated has been used to corroborate available lean geological and hydro-geological data on the Obi coal.

INTRODUCTION

Acid mine drainage (AMD) is the flow, or seepage, of polluted water from old mining areas which depending on the geology; the water may contain toxic heavy metals and radioactive particles. It is one of the most perpetual pollution problems confronting mining areas world-wide in the mining areas causing health problems to humans, as well as plants and animals AMD also refers to drainage resulting from the natural oxidation of sulphide minerals formed in mined rock or wastes [Geldenhuis 1997] or in other words it also refers to the distinctive type of wastewater that originates from the weathering and leaching of sulphide minerals present in coal and metalliferous ore bodies. Drainage results from various mining methods performed in the watershed. These methods include series of underground mining methods, such as Short wall, Longwall, Highwall mining methods, and surface and auger mining. The mining process exposes iron sulfide (pyrite) and un-removed coal contained in the sandstone overburden to air and water which are the major agents of chemical reactions. These oxidizing conditions result in an increase of acidity, which subsequently decreases the pH and increases the concentrations of dissolved metals in the water. These consequences lead to an overall degradation of water quality and the inability to support aquatic life [Sharma 2010].

AMD from abandoned coal mines affects the quality of both groundwater and surface water. Mineral production is an important component of the economy for many countries, and in some cases it can be the major source of international revenue. However, mining and mineral production operations that are not well managed can contaminate groundwater and surface water in the form of AMD, and can adversely affect the health of nearby communities that rely on this source for drinking-water, agriculture or recreation purposes. Water pumped from abandoned mine shafts and open-cut pits is often used for water supply, and is generally safe and reliable. However, these water sources may sometimes be contaminated by mineral processing chemicals, acid mine drainage (AMD) and waste disposal. These risks must be considered and assessed to determine whether such water sources are safe to be used for drinking-water supply.

AMD is probably the most severe environmental problem that occurs on mine sites. It happens where mineral and coal deposits contain sulfide minerals, particularly pyrite (FeS_2). When waste rock containing sulfides is exposed to air, these minerals are oxidized, releasing sulfuric acid. The process is accelerated by bacteria such as *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* that obtain energy from the oxidation reaction for their growth. The release of acid can cause the pH of surface water and groundwater to become very low (as low as 2). Under these very acidic conditions, metal concentrations in water can become very high due to the dissolution of elements from waste rock. Acidic water at mine sites have become a menace to many countries often hampering agriculture/vegetation, and may causing danger to aquatic life in rivers and ponds. It has become necessary to curb the excesses of AMD by adhering to relevant environmental controls.

Mine Drainage-An Overview

Acid mine drainage constitutes a serious problem in several operational and abandoned mines in developing and developed economies of Africa, Latin America, Asia, Europe, Canada and the United States of America . Examples being the eastern Transvaal Coal mines, South Africa, River Nyaba, Nigeria, Enugu Coal, Nigeria amongst several others. A major problem encountered in the supply of potable water to Enugu is the acid mine drainage pollution caused by coal mining activities in the area. The acid mine drainage water has elevated values of sulphate and iron ions and the pH is very low. Standing at 2.08 at Onyeama Mines, 2.3 at the Okpara Mine and 6.1 at the Iva Valley Coal Mine and 6.3 at the the active Obwetti fireclay Mine. The concentration of sulphate ions are high in the (acid mine drainage) waters. The corresponding values of 310mg/l, 420mg/l, 58mg/l, and 178mg/l have been recorded for the Onyeama, Okpara, Iva Valley and Obwetti Mines respectively. Thus, the mine water is acidic which corrodes mining and plumbing equipment. The water is also moderately hard and has high total dissolved solids (TDS) concentrations (Ezeigbo and Ezeanyim 2006). In Ishiagu Lead and Zinc (Pb/Zn) mine, over 60% of the mine drainage composition from the three mine pits are slightly acidic. The mean pH values ranged from 6.7 to 8.1 in wet season and 6.1 to 7.3 in dry season (Aroh 2003). Eze and Uko (2003) recorded a much lower mine pH of 5.6 and 5.1 for wet and dry season respectively in a separate study. Williams and Rose (1982) enumerated the factors that influence the generation of acid mine drainage to include abundant pyrites in overburden, presence of iron oxidizing bacteria and low pH (Eroh et al 2007).

Acid mine drainage (AMD) is Pennsylvania's single greatest source of water pollution, responsible for over 2,400 miles of polluted streams. Most, but not all, of this pollution is from discharges from mines abandoned before the 1964 amendment to the Clean Streams Law that required mine operators to treat mine drainage. Since that time, applicants for mining permits have been required to demonstrate that mining would not cause mine drainage pollution following reclamation of the mine. It was not until the early 1980s that post mining water quality could be predicted with any degree of reliability. Acid drainage problems exist in Pennsylvania, West Virginia, Ohio, Kentucky, Maryland, Indiana, Illinois, Oklahoma, Iowa, Missouri, Kansas, Tennessee, Virginia, Alabama, and Georgia. Pennsylvania and Northern West Virginia, the two most extensively mined states in Appalachia, lack limestone formations, and as a result experience severe acid drainage pollution (Todd and Reddick 1997). Several cases have occurred all over Canada where the metal from mines has combined with the acid from pyrite, resulting in the destruction of stream habitats. Similarly examples of mine drainage are associated with coal mines in Donbas (Russia), Ruhr coalfields (West Germany), and in Australia, India and Canada with predominant Shortwall mining. In India the coal mines are facing serious problems due to acid mine drainage particularly in the lower Gondwana coal of the Barakar formation, and the Tertiary coal of Assam (Jamal et al ; 1991). AMD has equally caused environmental problems in the Cornwall coal fields of England following centuries of coal mining.

The high level of success in preventing AMD especially in the developed economies is mostly due to advances in the science of AMD prevention and prediction. But it also speaks very well of the quality of DEP's permit review and compliance monitoring staff. Remediation of acid drainage is difficult and expensive. Many

companies use hydrated lime, sodium hydroxide, sodium carbonate, or ammonia to treat acid mine water, with each chemical offering the advantage of neutralizing acidity. Bactericides including antibiotics, heavy metals, detergents, and food preservatives have also been found to reduce acid mine drainage, however, antibiotics and heavy metals are too costly and also too dangerous to the surrounding aquatic life to be effectively used. Alconox, an inexpensive commercial detergent, and sodium lauryl sulfate both are found to reduce acid production in mine drainage (Hedin, et al 1994). In the United States, according to Watzlaf et al (2004), mining companies commonly treat contaminated drainage using conventional chemical methods. In most conventional treatment systems, metal contaminants are removed through the constantly measured addition of alkaline chemicals (e.g. NaOH, Ca (OH)₂, CaO, Na₂CO₃, or NH₃) to meet Federal effluent limits (Table 1).

Table 1; Federal Effluent Limits in USA for coal Mine Drainage

Parameter	Maximum for any One Day	Average of Daily Value for 30 Consecutive Days
Iron, total (mg/L)	6.0	3.0
Manganese ,total (mg/L)	4.0	2.0
Total Suspended Solids(mg/L)	70	35
pH (Standard Units)	Between 6.0 and 9.0	Between 6.0 and 9.0

Source: Watzlaf et al. 2004

Geology of Lafia-Obi Coal

The geological investigation of the Lafia-Obi coal fields carried out by the Exploration and Mining Division of the National Steel Council, Kaduna between 1973 to 1979 established a commercial reserve of 128,304,000 tons of coal [NSC 1978]. The reserve which is strategic for Nigerians' metallurgical industry for its coking properties is bounded by Latitudes 8° 25' 43" N and 8° 20' 40" N in its northern and Southern boundaries, and by longitudes 8° 48' 80" E and 8° 55' 55" E on its eastern and western boundaries. This reserve is expected to be exploited by underground mining methods.

The structural geology of the Lafia-Obi area is expected to play a major role in water drainage in the cause of mining of the coal. The structure of the Obi coal is linked with the tectonic history of the Benue trough which is tied with the opening of the south Atlantic, during which geologic episode, the thick sediments that accumulated in it were thrown into series of south-Westerly trending open folds and cut by numerous faults that trend east-west [NSC 1978]. The area is composed of series of synclines and anticlines trending from (north-east) to (south-east) notable amongst which are the Agyaragu, Adabu, Obi, Giza and Kadarko anticlines. The coal deposit occurs within the Giza anticline. The Obi faults have so far been mapped within the study area with vertical throws range from 45m to 125m and deep angles of approximately 45° to 75°.

Surface and Groundwater Hydrology

The drainage pattern of the study area is separated by a ridge structure separating Lafia-Obi and Kwashiri /Agwatashi prospecting shafts. The drainages flow north-southwards towards Lafia Obi and north-eastwards from the separating ridge respectively.

In order that acid mine drainage takes effect, the presence of water is paramount. The results of investigation by the Steel Council as corroborated by the satellite image indicates that the influence of both sub-surface and surface drainages shall play a role in acid mine drainage in the process of development and mining of the Obi coal (Figs 1, 2 and 3). These images show elevation of the study area above sea level, river networks and lineaments which reveal highly fractured underlain rocks. Generally on the Eastern part of the map is highly fractured as compared with the western part of the study area. The effects of mine drainage are more likely to affect the town of Obi and its environs because of the presence of these high fractures which trend generally in the South- East; and North- West directions.

The topography of the study area shows that a ridge separates the towns of Lafia and Obi (with a pick height of 750ft above sea level). It gently undulates up to 650ft North- West of Kwashiri shaft, and then rises up to 700ft at Akudi area North West of the shaft Agwashiri. The 3D map corroborates the trend of the flow directions of

the tributaries. The four picks control the flows of the tributaries generally. Tributaries flowing from Agode, Akodi, Iyorugwa and Agaza empty into the river Ankwe which subsequently empties itself into the River Benue. However, the tributaries of Obi, Ume and Adobi empty themselves directly into the River Benue. The influence of the four hilly picks proves a hydrological centre with dominant flow in a Southwards direction. In the Lafia area the tributaries flow in the North-West direction. On the Obi side the flow is in two directions; North-East and South- South- East. The effect of mine drainage from the above description is likely to affect Shendam which is located to the North East and Keana located to the south East. It is however believed that for this to take effect, the fractures and drainages must contribute. The mining method to be employed vis-à-vis the choice of the location of the rock waste disposal dumb will also contribute to areas to be polluted by AMD. The choice of waste dump location should take into consideration the nature of terrain and underlain rock structure.

Fig.1 Satellite Image Map of the study are showing the surface drainage

Fig.2 Contour and 3D Diagram of the Topography of the Study Area

Fig.3 Satellite Image showing the topography

Chemistry and role of water in Acid Mine Drainage

The Obi coal deposit and the surrounding country rocks do not constitute any environmental problems. In their undisturbed form the rocks are free of contamination. However the danger will surface at the point where the activities of mining start. These activities include detailed prospecting mine development and subsequent mining of coal. In the process the ground would have to be disturbed through drilling, blasting and loading/haulages of the rock and coal materials to either waste dumps or processing plants. Most times the association of sulfide's with metallic ores and fossil fuels in the form of pyrite (FeS_2) and the world's increasing demand for metals and fossil fuels, makes sulfide oxidation in nature to be in some state of perturbation. This perturbation, which results from land disturbances (e.g. mining, and/or ore processing), produces acid drainage which is often enriched with heavy metals. The rate of pyrite oxidation depends on the following: reactive surface area of the pyrite, the oxygen concentration and pH of the water, the forms of pyrite, and the presence of Fe-oxidizing bacteria (*Thiobacillus ferroxidans*).

Acid mine drainage is an extremely acidic iron and sulphate rich drainage that forms under natural conditions when certain coal seams are mined and the associated strata are exposed to a new oxidizing environment. During this process, a variety of iron sulphides are exposed to the atmosphere and oxidized in the presence of oxygen and water to form soluble hydrous iron sulphates. Some of the oxidation compound products have been identified as *melanterite* (white crystals of FeSO_4), *copiapite* (yellow crystals of ferric sulphate $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$), *halotrichite* (white crystals of iron and/ or magnesium aluminium sulphate), and *alunogenite* (white crystals of aluminum sulphate). These compounds usually appear in hydrated form as yellow and white crusts along certain horizons on the exposed surfaces of the pyritic material in coal mines.

During the mining process, a sulfide containing compound can be uncovered. One of the most common examples is when pyrite (FeS_2) is disturbed during the mining process. Once exposed to the oxygen in the air and the water surrounding the mine, the pyrite reacts in a series of steps ending with the formation of sulfuric acid. This sulfuric acid percolates by seeping into the underground waterways/surface streams and polluting the area surrounding the mine for several kilometers. The reaction of pyrite with oxygen and water is really quite simple and is as follows:

1st Step: The pyrite oxidizes upon contact with air and water.

2nd Step: Iron oxidizes to ferric iron.

3rd Step: Precipitation occurs with ferric iron to ferric hydroxide.

4th Step: All combined to show a full formation of sulfuric acid.

The acidity is caused when the hydrogen (H^+) ions are released into the water in one of the above steps. This reaction can sometimes occur many years after a mine has shut down. Once in the waterways, the sulfuric acid lowers the pH of the streams, rivers, etc. virtually killing anything that cannot handle the stress of the stronger acidity levels. The acid in the water neutralizes the carbonate and bicarbonate ions resulting in the formation of carbonic acid (HCO), which weakens the natural buffering action of the water. When the buffering system is unable to react anymore, usually at a pH of 4.2, the water way suddenly becomes acidic and it is too late to reverse the damage. Also, another hazardous reaction resulting directly from the lowering of the pH comes from the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ precipitating out in the water. It affects streams by blocking sunlight and covering the stream bed with a thick red blanket. Acid mine drainage becomes hazardous to the environment, thus disrupting the cycle of nature (*Lawhorn ,2010*).

Another way acid mine drainage affects the area is from the deposits of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ or other metallic compounds. A reaction occurs that results in a heavy sedimentation that blankets the stream. This "blanket" discolors the stream and covers up vegetation and/or prey on which larger aquatic animals depend. This blanket is caused when the iron hydroxide precipitates out of the water due to a lower pH from acid mine drainage. Not only does it cover food, but it also blocks out sunlight important for photosynthesis in plants. When the plants die, the rest of the aquatic cycle is upset and ultimately the stream becomes barren (Baird;Colin 1995).

Environmental and Ecological effects of Acid Mine Drainage

Acidity and metal toxicity: The high acidity of acid mine drainage and the high amounts of dissolved heavy metals (such as copper and zinc) generally make acid mine drainage extremely toxic to most organisms. Many streams derived from acid mine drainage are largely devoid of life for a long way downstream.

Sedimentation: Drainage water from acid mine drainage is initially clear but turns a vivid orange colour as it becomes neutralised because of the precipitation of iron oxides and hydroxides. This precipitate, often called ochre, is very fine and smothers the river bed with very fine silt. Thus, small animals that used to feed on the bottom of the stream or ocean (benthic organisms) can no longer feed and so are depleted. Because these animals are at the bottom of the aquatic food chain, this has impacts higher up the food chain into fish.

Effects on marine ecosystem: Acid mine drainage will be neutralised by the sea, unless it is already neutralised. The ochre (orange precipitate) may be formed in the sea as the stream enters the sea, or the ochre is formed in the stream and washed in to the sea by the stream. There is potential for acid mine drainage to influence the food chain in the near vicinity, resulting in possible negative effects on the whales, shark and other marine life.

Assessing the impact - When assessing the impact of industrial discharges on receiving waters, the most critical characteristics are:

1. The types of chemicals discharged, depends on the type of industries and processes used.
2. The amount and concentration of chemicals in the effluent vary over time depending on the operation mode of both manufacturing and wastewater treatment processes employed (e.g. hourly, daily, weekly, monthly and seasonal variations).
3. Solid wastes and/or gaseous emission generated from industrial sources also contribute to the amount and concentration of chemicals in the effluent if they are treated with water or they have any contact with water.

Control of Acid Mine Drainage

If generation of AMD cannot be prevented, it must be collected and treated. Treatment of AMD usually costs more than control of AMD and may be required for many years after mining activities have ceased. Therefore, application of appropriate control methods to the site at the early stage of the mining would be beneficial. Although prevention of AMD is the most desirable option, a cost-effective prevention method is not yet available. The most effective method of control is to minimize penetration of air and water through the waste pile using a cover, either wet (water) or dry (soil), which is placed over the waste pile. Despite their high cost, these covers cannot always completely stop the oxidation process and generation of AMD. Application of more than one option might be required. Early diagnosis of the problem, identification of appropriate prevention/control measures and implementation of these methods to the site would reduce the potential risk of AMD generation. AMD prevention/control measures broadly include use of covers, control of the source, migration of AMD, and treatment.

AMD abatement Methods - The formation and treatment of acid mine drainage is the biggest environmental problems relating to mining and processing activities worldwide. Various methods are used for the sulphates and heavy metals removal from acid mine drainage in the world. There are two approaches to controlling Acid Mine Drainage. The first is to reduce or eliminate the source of the AMD. One method for source elimination seeks to prevent oxidation by replacing the air within the mine with groundwater. This air-with-water replacement is brought about by sealing any mine openings with an impermeable grouting material. One such material under investigation is flue gas desulfurization (FGD) material, a by-product from coal-fired power plants. This material is composed of primarily calcium sulfate (gypsum). Another source elimination strategy is to fill the mine with a solid (e.g., FGD or a clay slurry) in order to eliminate the oxidation reaction.

The second primary method for mitigating Acid Mine Drainage involves treating the AMD itself in order to remove the negative impact to the watershed. Chemical, biological, or physical treatments may be used in AMD abatement. Chemical treatments primarily seek to neutralize the acid through the addition of an alkali (e.g., soda ash) with a subsequent sedimentation basin in order to retain metal precipitates after the pH adjustment. Biological treatments use constructed wetlands, as one example, for natural attenuation of biological nutrient additions in order to accelerate indigenous activity. Physical treatment seeks to alleviate the impact through re-routing of streams to circumvent possible problematic geological formations.

In environments where groundwater has been contaminated by waste water and acid mine drainage, microbial sulfate reduction can be exploited in subsurface permeable reactive barriers. A permeable reactive barrier is a passive, in-situ technique: groundwater treatment proceeds within the aquifer and long-term maintenance of the installation is unnecessary. This method consists of installing an appropriate reactive material into the aquifer, so that contaminated water flows through the material. The reactive material induces chemical reactions that remove the contaminants from the water or otherwise cause a change that decreases the toxicity of the contaminated water.

CONCLUSION

The development and mining of the Obi metallurgical coal is by all means a welcome development in Nigeria's quest to develop the Steel Industry for national economic growth and development. However the process is saddled with environment problems that can either be short or long terms as the case have been with similar mines worldwide. The geology of the Obi coal presently favours the underground mining method of extraction. The process of development and mining is expected to interfere with the hydrological balance of the entire Lafia-obi areas, in terms of both surface and underground hydrology with a resultant consequence of the emergence of polluted water detrimental to humans, plants/vegetation, and aquatic life alike. This effect is likely to be aggravate and / or supported by the structural geology of under lain rocks and topography which appear from geological and satellite imagery studies to be highly fractured with numerous streams, rivers, and aquifers as potential agents of transmissions of Acid Mine Drainage.

The paper is meant to preempt the envisaged and/ or pending environmental problems associated with the development and mining of the Obi Coking coal deposits which must need to be effectively captured in the Environmental impact Assessment of mining of this important mineral commodity. The essence is to ensure that appropriate control and remediation measures are maintained throughout the life span of mining. This is to safeguard against any catastrophic effect especially on the Lafia Obi towns and villages either in the course of mining or in post mining periods. Nigeria's mine regulations must ensure an affirmative demonstration that

mining of the Obi coal will not cause pollution. While AMD can readily be treated with current technology in the course of mining, long-term drainage, which persists after mining has ceased, may persist for decades or even centuries to the detriment of the immediate community. This should be guarded against.

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